

Impact analysis of Music Therapy in Human and Albino rats on the hemato-biochemical parameters related with cardiovascular disorders.

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Abstract

Today we are living in the sea of chemicals using them in most of our daily activity, which are responsible for creating various type of disease or disorder to cure them we are using chemicals in form of drug. There is no doubt that drugs have the ability to cure them, but on the other side it is a well establish fact that each drug have some short of side effects on our body and some time side effects are converting in to serious problems leading upto death. On the other side today's hectic life style and working stress creating various types of health

Music therapy using since time immemorial and It is an established fact that brain is controlling entire metabolism, biochemistry, haematology, physiology etc. of the body, So anything which is capable to influence the brain also influences the entire metabolism and physiology of body. No doubt this can be done by sound vibrations in form of music.

*In the present study the effect of specific sounds analyzed through biochemical analysis of **Adrenalin, Cortisol, Triglyceride, Cholesterol, LDL, VLDL and HDL** level in the blood of albino rat (lab condition) and Humans (volunteers) for a three months (30, 60 and 90 days protocol) treatment period.*

Observations are so surprising. The biochemical parameters altered significantly in rats, while in humans most parameters altered none significant to very highly significant. The difference in significance level of humans and rats shows that there is factor which is responsible to affect the result in lab and field condition, but it is clear from the present findings that music has the power to affect the hemato-biochemistry of livings and it should be need more investigation from different aspects

Key Words: *Music Therapy, Adrenalin, Cortisol, Lipids, Cholesterol, Lipoproteins*

Introduction

Today we are living in the sea of chemicals. We are using them in most of our activity for making our life easy. They can do this but on the other side they are also responsible for creating various type of disease or disorder to cure them we are again using chemicals in form of drug. There is no doubt that drugs have the ability to cure them, but on the other side it is a well establish fact that each drug have some short of side effects on the body of livings including human body and some time side effects are converting in to serious problems leading up to death. On the other side today's

hectic life style and working stress creating various types of health problems such unusual B.P., Cardiovascular problems, headache, depression, sleeplessness, nervous problems etc. which are sometime converted in to serious problems and effecting the family life & working efficiency of the person. Music therapy using since time immemorial and It is an established fact that brain is controlling entire metabolism, biochemistry, haematology, physiology etc. of the body, So anything which is capable to influence the brain also influences the entire metabolism and physiology of body. No doubt this can be done by sound vibrations in form of music. Music can be use as non-pharmacological aids to the patients of various disorders which are related with the imbalance of various biochemicals«s studied during the present study.

Music therapy is an allied health profession and a field of scientific research, which studies correlations between the process of clinical therapy and bio-musicology. Indian classical 'Ragas' have been acclaimed by Vedic science to have healing effects. Music has frequently been used as a therapeutic agent from the ancient times. In India, music is a kind of yoga system through the medium of sonorous sound, which acts upon the human organism and awakens and develops their proper functions to the extent of self-realization, which is the ultimate goal of Philosophy of all religion. Melody is the keynote of Indian Music. There are countless 'Ragas' of course with countless characteristic peculiarities of their own. That is why we cannot establish a particular Raga for a particular disease. Different types of Ragas are applied in each different case. When the term Music Therapy is used, we think world-wide system of therapy. Literature of Vocal part of Indian Classical Music is not sufficient in that case. Classical music with its unique swara/note structure ensures calm and cozy mind by exposure and subdues the emotion provoking situations. Music plays an effective role in subduing the so-called emotional imbalance.

Present study is plan to evaluate the effect of different type of sound on hemato-biochemical parameters related with the cardiovascular disorders.

Material and Methods

Selection of Music (Test compound)

Music is selected on the basis of their property. Specific Indian ragas are selected for the treatment of Albino rat, where as for human volunteers specific songs selected from the list they provided in questionnaire, based on specific Indian Ragas.

Three sets of pre-recorded Indian classical sound are selected on the basis of trial and error methods. They are given to the experimental animals for a period of 90 days. The biochemical analysis of blood samples are carried at 30days, 60days and 90 days. The results were analyzed and after that the similar sound treatment are given to volunteers for a period of 90 days. The biochemical analysis of blood samples are carried at 30days, 60days and 90 days interval. The blood samples of volunteers are collected by a physician hire for the purpose, where as the blood of albino rats was taken in lab from treated and control groups.

Sound of specific Indian ragas at a 60-80 db (controlled by sound meter) are given to albino rat for two hours (9-10 AM and 3-4 PM) daily by speakers attached to the wall of their cage for 30,60,90 days through , where as human volunteers are allowed to listened a specific songs based on ragas through head phones provided them at home (for the same time period as to rats) after training them in workshops organized in dept« on Sundays and holidays.

Control groups of both rats and humans are also assigned to listening to taped "white noise" ("White noise" or "synthetic silence" is an attempt to block out environmental noise. In this case it was a pre nature sounds such as sea sounds, which themselves were rhythmic) through

headphones, or to a control group.

Maintenance and Feeding of Experimental Albino Rats- *The experimental albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus* [Berkenhout]), procured from inbred colony were acclimated for one month to the laboratory conditions (temperature. $25\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$, relative humidity $60\pm 5\%$ and photoperiod 12 hr/day) before using them for the experiment. Adult male and female rats of almost equal size and weight were kept in the polypropylene cages and cleaned regularly to avoid any infection or undesirable odour in the laboratory. Each cage was equipped with a metallic food plate and water bottle. The albino rats were offered fresh feed daily throughout the experimentation on Gold Mohar rat and mice feed, manufactured by Hindustan Lever Ltd., India at regular interval and water was provided *ad libitum*.*

Selection of Individuals-

Albino Rats: *For the experimentation individuals selected randomly irrespective of sex. Five healthy adult albino rats (6–8 weeks of age, with average body weight of 150–200 g) were selected randomly for test and control studies their blood was collected after 30, 60 and 90 days for the present investigation. Each rat was assigned a number for convenience prior to experimentation.*

Volunteers- *The Volunteers were selected through a wide publicity (News paper, SMS, TV Programmes) from Agra, Noida, Delhi, Gaziabad, Gurgawn region. They are provided to fill a questionnaire. On the basis of a questionnaire they are provide a recorded CD of selected songs and sounds.*

Collection of Blood Samples

The blood from rats collected in the early morning hours (7-8 AM) in lab on the scheduled date. The blood samples were obtained with the help of 2.0 ml disposable syringe from the tail albino rats, Whereas the blood samples of human were collected by a physician hired for the purpose. The various biochemical parameters of rats were analyzed with the help of a standard kit methods in dept lab, while human blood test are conducted in authorize labs of a respective city.

Results

Table-I:

Parameters	Albino Rat (In Lab)			Human Volunteers		
	Sound A	Sound B	Sound C	Sound A	Sound B	Sound C
Adrenalin	?S	?S	?S	?NS	?NS	?NS
Cortisol	?S	?NS	?S	?S	?NS	?S
TG	?NS	?NS	?S	?NS	?NS	?S
CHO	?HS	?NS	?S	?VHS	?NS	?VHS
LDL	?NS	?NS	?S	?NS	?NS	?S
HDL	?S	?S	?NS	?HS	?S	?NS
VLDL	?NS	?NS	?S	?NS	?NS	?S

Significant Level: $P < 0.001$ (VHS=Very Highly Significant), $P < 0.01$ (HS=Highly Significant), $P < 0.05$ (S=Significant), $P > 0.05$ (NS=Non significant),

Discussion

Significant ($P < 0.001$ to $P < 0.05$) decrease has been found in serum total cholesterol level in both human. In most cases Non Significant decrease in Triglycerides has been observed except in all cases except sound "C" where significant decrease observed. Lipid bound proteins are called lipoproteins. Lipoproteins are found in plasma and their function is to transport lipids. Lipoprotein includes VLDL, LDL and HDL. In the present study VLDL and LDL are decrease Non significantly except in case of sound "C". The HDL significantly increased in most cases. The decrease of serum triglycerides, cholesterol are directly correlated with decrease of LDL and VLDL. The decreases of various lipids are indicative of good health. And support the view that sound can be use as a drug to control various lipid parameters. In the present study sound increase the adrenalin level in both rat and human, whereas cortisol level fond to be decreased.

Most of the above biochemical findings of present investigation are helpful to establish doctrine that music can be use for various cardiovascular disorders, but there is fluctuation between different sound and biochemical parameters, so it needs more study to establish a fact that "X" sound can be use as for a specific bio-molecule responsible for a CVD. The present findings gain support the work done various researcher around the world as mentioned below.

The effect of music on the cardiovascular disorders have been initially evident in "Lancet" (medical journal), In which Vincent and Thompson (1929) made an attempt to discover the influence of listening to gramophone, and radio, music on blood pressure and he observed that listening to music was accompanied by a slight rise in blood pressure in the listener. Bason and Celler (1972) observed that the human heart rate could be varied over a certain range by entrainment of the sinus rhythm with external auditory stimulus. Bason's paper is important for supporting the proposition often made by music therapists that meeting the tempo of the patient influences their musical playing and is the initial key to therapeutic change.

An extension of this premise, that musical rhythm is a pacemaker, was investigated by Haas et al. (1986) in terms of the effects of perceived rhythm on respiratory pattern, a pattern that serves both metabolic and behavioral functions. He hypothesized that an external rhythmical musical activity, in this case listening to taped music.

Several authors have investigated this relationship in the setting of hospital care (Bonny 1983; Davis et al. 1987; Zimmerman et al. 1988; Guzzetta 1989; Philip 1989; Elliott 1994) often with the intent of reducing anxiety in chronically ill patients (Gross and Swartz 1982; Standley 1986), for treating anxiety in general (Robb 2000), or specifically in musicians (Brodsky and Sloboda 1997).

Bonny (1978,1983) has suggested a series of musical selections for tape recordings which can be chosen for their sedative effects and according to other mood criteria, associative imagery and relaxation potential, none of which have been empirically confirmed. For this Updike (1990) conducted an experiment and confirms Bonny's impression that there is a decreased systolic blood pressure,

and a beneficial mood change from anxiety to relaxed calm, when sedative music is played.

Rider (1985a,b) explained that disease related stress was caused by the desynchronization of circadian oscillators and that listening to sedative music, with a guided imagery induction, would promote the entrainment of circadian rhythms as expressed in temperature and corticosteroid levels of nursing staff. This study found no conclusive results, mainly because there was no control group.

Guzzetta (1989) conducted a study to determine whether relaxation and music therapy were effective in reducing stress in patients admitted to a coronary care unit with the presumptive diagnosis of acute myocardial infarction. In this experimental study, 80 patients were randomly assigned to a relaxation, music therapy, or control group. Music therapy was comprised of a relaxation induction and listening to a 20 minute musical cassette tape selected from three alternative musical styles; soothing classical music, soothing popular music and non-traditional music. Stress was evaluated by apical heart rates, peripheral temperatures, cardiac complications, and qualitative patient evaluative data. Data analysis revealed that lowering apical heart rates and raising peripheral temperatures were more successful in the relaxation and music therapy groups than in the control group. The incidence of cardiac complications was found to be lower in the intervention groups, and most intervention subjects believed that such therapy was helpful. Both relaxation and music therapy were found to be effective modalities of reducing stress in these patients, and music listening was more effective than relaxation alone. Furthermore, apical heart rates were lowered in response to music over a series of sessions thus supporting the argument that the assessment of music therapy on physiological parameters is dependent upon adaptation over time. Further research strategies may wish to make longitudinal studies of the influence of music on physiological parameters.

Bason«s (1972) study could influence heart rate by matching the heart rate of the patient, then we must conclude that studies of the influence of music on heart rate must match the music to the individual patient. This also makes psychological sense as different people have varied reactions to the same music. Furthermore, improvised music playing which takes meeting the tempo of the patient as one of its main principles may have an impact other than the passive listening to music. In addition, the work of Haas (Haas et al. 1986) mentioned above showed that listening, coupled with tapping, synchronizes respiration pattern with musical rhythm, further emphasizing that active music playing can be used to influence physiological parameters and that this synchronization can be learned.

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